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Research Article

**THE KNOWLEDGE RELATED TO THE GYNECOLOGICAL
LAPAROSCOPIC SURGERIES: DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH
STUDY IN ALLIED HOSPITAL, FAISALABAD****Dr. Haseeb Masood, Dr. Muhammad Mansoor Ijaz, Dr. Muhammad Noman Tahir**
House Officer, DHQ Hospital Faisalabad**Abstract:**

Aims: The purpose of this research paper was to share the knowledge related to the gynecological laparoscopic surgeries in Allied Hospital, Faisalabad.

Study Design: Descriptive research study.

Place and Duration: Carried out Present detailed study with effect from February 2017 to April, 2018 in Allied Hospital, Faisalabad.

Methods: All of us made a detailed study with effect from February 2017 to April, 2018 for the patient's analyzation. We have examined the 218 peoples, out of those mostly of them were between the age of twenty-seven to thirty years old (25%). The cases of ectopic pregnancy had the number of 28 (13%) and the cases of Ovarian Cyst had the number of 111 (52%). The patients faced the gynecological laparoscopic surgeries their factors, difficulties and types of procedures.

Results: Examined total of 218 patients carefully selected for the study. The cases of ectopic pregnancy had the number of 28 (13%) and the cases of Ovarian Cyst had the number of 111 (52%). There had 8 patients, ovarian cystectomy or hysterectomy and cholecystectomy surgeons treated them. There were 32 patients of laparoscopy, we diagnosed. Laparoscopic hysterectomy had checked in 33 patients. Laparotomy exchange took place in 8 patients and only one patient had the vascular problems. There had the ordinary and constant complaints of pain in different degrees of post-operation. These complaints over came through parenteral and oral analgesics. Oral medication via its way adopted with effect from fourth / sixth hours and after completion of a day progress had begun. 164 cases admitted in hospital and medicated for two days (75%) and rest of the 53 patients (25%) got medication for more than two days and longer period

Conclusion: Laparoscopic surgery may control post -operative ache according to the examination of patients. This as well minimized the size of scream on post-operation and also taught that medication and admission is compulsory at medical Centre for the entire and instant improvement. Hence satisfactory expertise and proficient teaching staff is compulsory for Victorious and accomplished laparoscopic operations.

Keywords: Gynecological Laparoscopic Surgeries (GLS) and Hysterectomy. Cystectomy

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INTRODUCTION:

Laparoscopy has a value of innovative accumulation in gynecological surgical operation and marked as fewer persistent and secure too. The inventor of the method was Jacobeus and was the resident of Sweden [3] The people adopted it warm heartedly in beginning but after some time things changed. The initial hurdle of this was the physically activity and knowledge of surveys of endoscopy surgery. Crawling Tubal sterilization had the first ever laparoscopic gynecological surgery took place in Nepali hospital. So as resultant they have crowded phase to setting it in the countries which are in developing phase. In early stage, gynecology utilized these procedures for purpose of identification, after passing the time this they utilized it for the difficulties and troubles of gynecology. as by the Padhye, among the 1600 laparoscopic sterilization cases detected by using this simple, economical and acceptable skill. The purpose of this research paper was to share the knowledge related to the gynecological laparoscopic surgeries in the Allied Hospital, Faisalabad.

METHODOLOGY:

Carried out detailed study from February 2017 to April, 2018 for the analysis of patients. The patients faced the gynecological laparoscopic surgeries, their reasons of occurrence, difficulties and types of procedures. Before conducting of this this research, we met with the ethical committee of the hospital and seek authorization from them. All participants of the examination group had briefed about type, method of conductivity, prior and post of operation problems, its need, medication and detention in hospital. We evaluate all the patients prior to operation such as

clinical reports, inquiries, scan beneath the waist area and tumor determination. All of patients admitted in hospital, who we selected for under gone the operative intestine preparation. All patients had endotracheal intubation general anesthesia. While practicing the patients had set at place of lithotomy Trendelenburg. The tummy had exposed by using the cannula open method. Total laparoscopic hysterectomy (TLH) took place by using common technique with the assistance of end suture or vault cloure by vaginally. Creation of pneumoperitoneum took place and an infra treated umbilical. They removed cyst from ovary by using the deroofting followed by oophorectomy or ovarian cyst enucleating aspirating or cyst wall removal as the requirement. Routine health Centre expanded to all patients' parenteral antibiotics during first day and given the antibiotics by mouth for next 5 days. Some of the affected patients got free from hospital at normal stay of one day at hospital like cystectomy patients and Diagnostic laparoscopy patients. Meanwhile some cases of TLH got medication and stayed for seventy-two hours at hospital. Transcription period of all the cases were about one week observed for record.

RESULTS:

we have examined the 218 peoples, out of those mostly of them were between the age of twenty-seven to thirty years old (25%). The cases of ectopic pregnancy had the number of 28 (13%) and the cases of Ovarian Cyst had the number of 111 (52%). We had found the large symptoms of infertility in the 12 cases of analytical laparoscopy. Lap cystectomy was like normal surgery as mentioned in Table No 1.

Table No 1: Types of laparoscopic procedures

<i>Types of procedures</i>	Percentage	Frequency
<i>TLH</i>	16 %	33
<i>LAVH</i>	03 %	07
<i>Lap salpingectomy</i>	13 %	27
<i>Bilateral tubal ligation</i>	02 %	03
<i>Diagnostic Laparoscopy</i>	15 %	32
<i>Lap Oophorectomy</i>	05 %	10
<i>Lap Cystectomy</i>	46 %	97

Table No 2: Indications for diagnostic laparoscopy

Details	Percentage
DUB	12 %
Others (CIN, Chr cervicitis)	06 %
Adenomyosis	05 %
Uterine Fibroid	10 %

Total laparoscopic hysterectomy main frequent symptoms found as bleeding of dysfunctional uterine as mentioned in Table No 3.

Table No 3: Indications for total Laparoscopic Hysterectomy

Details	Percentage
Endometriosis	06 %
Pelvic Pain	04 %
Sub-fertility	12 %
PCOS	03 %
Others (Acute Abdomen, Cur Removal)	07 %

Different type of technical hitches mentioned in table four about the methods of laparoscopic. There had 10 patients of port site viruses, out of them there were two patients who had the need of re-suturing. 08 cases had dealt with laparotomy alteration.

Table No 4: Complications of the procedure

Complication Types	Percentage	Frequency
<i>Port site infection requiring re-suturing</i>	0.9 %	2
<i>Vault infection</i>	1.3 %	3
<i>Vascular injury</i>	0.46 %	1
<i>Bowel/ bladder injury</i>	0 %	0
<i>Conversion to laparotomy</i>	3.6 %	8
<i>Pain, nausea, vomiting</i>	9.2 %	20
<i>Port site infection</i>	4.6 %	10

DISCUSSION:

like most students, the examinant took care of analytical methods and researches methods of laparoscopic operation, those analyzed that at evaluation to the analytical methods the occurrences were hundred and eighty-five patients beside thirty-two patients as mentioned in table. Most symptoms consist of subfertility and endometriosis for the progress of analytical laparoscopy due to occurrence of pelvic chronic ache. Like some different studies they took miscarriage an essential figure and symptoms of laparoscopy analysis [5, 6]. While the patients of PCOD, operation of ovary had conducted in experience of laparoscopic analysis.

In clinical theory we examined the ninety-seven / two seventy-one patients, changing to laparotomy investigated in 3 members because of the vessel damages and severe viscous. General kind cancer of ovary had 55 percent cystadenoma, twenty percent endometriosis and dermoid 26 percent. They treated Ovariectomy in 10 patients. This is similar with results of Shah. Endometriosis and Dermoid cysts are two reoccurred kind of ovary cancer according to Yuen papers. Same consequences have gotten by Parker at the 96 percent achievements as seventy five percent patients had laparoscopic cystectomy. Port site umbilical disease was the routine problems which they noticed in examination and found in ten patients as mentioned in table. The procedure of opening of supra and infra-umbilical were fine but it is decidable that which one is best [9].

According to Hasson examination papers, they examined the 16000 patients and they found four percent patients infected [8]. They carried out the re-suturing of two patients. We had the only one patient of vascular problem. Patients were totally comforting and fit after the replacing of the 1-point blood later the surgery. Nixer was the effect of the right outer iliac tube cauterization in the route of cyst enucleation, which needed for the early and immediate laparotomy to stop the blood. Colleagues noticed the same conditions [9].

As said by Yuen, Yuen and Parker resulted as for the kind unusual people have the wish of dealing is to be effective laparoscopy [10,11,12]. 27 patients of ectopic pregnancies faced laparoscopic salpingectomy. Hemoperitoneum migration took place in two patients to eliminate the abortion. laparoscopic management made treatment of the patients of Hemodynamically stable and they treated them during 24 hours that considered the restriction of laparoscopic treatment in case of any urgency. As

per Olagendoye laparoscopic administration & laparotomy was secure & practicable correspondingly in 59% and 29% of opening laparoscopy [13]. Many further writers did compare laparotomy & laparoscopic administration for pregnancies support laparoscopic operations at occurrence of removed pregnancy [14].

07 patients medicated at the accomplished velocity through (LAVH) laparoscopic assisted vaginal hysterectomy particularly in fibroid uterus in initial ages. After that TLH got suitable & thirty-three patients got medication due to this method. There were twelve DUB patients, five occurrences of adenomyosis, ten occurrences of fibroid uterus and other various patients shown in table [15]. A clinical examination had organized in 1995 shows that the laparoscopic hysterectomy threat is like abdominal hysterectomy & vaginal via specialist, as the Riberio noticed the same, that he declares abdominal hysterectomy and comparable laparoscopic hysterectomy [1]. They finalized that almost approximate 11/2-day detention at hospital in situation of analytical surgeries of laparoscopic, for hysterectomy situations three days and for sake of cystectomy situations two days needed. The early study paper 2 to 6 days detention had noticed and mentioned [1, 2].

As per Olagendoye laparoscopic supervision and laparotomy is secure and practical in sixty-two and thirty one percent of the patients individually after initial laparoscopy. Some researchers discussed comparatively laparoscopic supervision and laparoscopy for ectopic pregnancy in favor to laparoscopic operations in occurrence with ectopic pregnancies.

CONCLUSION:

Laparoscopic surgery may control post -operative ache according to the examination of patients. This as well minimized the size of scream on post-operation and also taught that medication and admission is compulsory at medical Centre for the entire and instant improvement. Hence satisfactory expertise and proficient teaching staff is compulsory for Victorious and accomplished laparoscopic operations.

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